

EVMPR : Estimated facial View representation based on Multivariate Polynomial Regression

Amina Kammoun¹, Tarek Ouni¹, Mohamed Abid¹, Rim Slama², et Hedi Tabia³

¹ CES-LAB, National Engineering School of Sfax, University of Sfax, Tunisia
amina.kammoun@enis.tn, tarek.ouni@gmail.com, mohamed.abid_ces@yahoo.fr

² LINEACT, CESI Lyon, France
rsalmi@cesi.fr

³ IBISC, Evry University, University of Paris Saclay, France.
hedi.tabia@univ-evry.fr

Abstract Cross-pose face recognition in the wild is an important problem in computer vision. The important variance between different views makes it challenging to differentiate between identities with a large intra-class variation. Multi-view modeling approaches require data sets with different views per person which are expensive in terms of collection and training, while Generative models generate new faces to augment and improve datasets. This paper presents a novel system, called EVMPR, that directly generates reduced facial representations in different poses from a single one basing on the multivariate polynomial regression between correlated features.

Key words Cross-pose, face recognition, one-to-many view generation, feature extraction, feature selection, feature correlation, multivariate polynomial regression.

1 Introduction

Face recognition has been one of the most significant research areas [10,16] in computer vision for several decades. Despite, the progress in this field, the performances of the existent models hardly correspond to the requirements of the real-world problem especially cross-pose variation. In fact, most face recognition algorithms performances decrease by over 10% [13] from frontal-frontal to frontal-profile verification. The problem is caused by the important variation in facial features between frontal and profile views.

Previous methods [2,7] address this problem either with models and/or face sets improvements. The improvement in the model is based on optimizing the feature extraction step. Some works [16,8], show that Deep Learning-based techniques especially Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) architectures are excellent in feature extraction compared to older techniques. In addition, the architecture can be optimized by using assembled networks with multiple inputs or multiple tasks instead of backbone ones.

The improvement in dataset can either be by many-to-one face normalization or one-to-many augmentation. Many-to-one face normalization methods frontalize and align faces in order to reduce the appearance variability of faces and compare easily between them. In recent works [16], autoencoder, Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), and Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) architectures are applied in Many-to-one face normalization.

One-to-many augmentation consists of generating many face images in different views from a single image. Many techniques are used in one-to-many data generation as 3D models, 2D deep models, data augmentation models and GANs models. 3D Models [16,12,9] consist of 3D face reconstruction models from 2D images then projecting them into 2D images in different poses. 2D deep Models [16,19,18] mainly based on CNN models, generate directly face images from one face view. Data augmentation models [15,6] repose on photometric and geometric transformations based on oversampling, rotation and the mirroring of images. The augmentation of training dataset improves the performance of face recognition systems in the real world. GAN based models [17,11,16] generate faces in different poses in order to improve cross-pose face recognition.

The proposed method, EVMPR, consists of generating reduced facial representation in different poses from a single view based on multivariate polynomial regression between correlated facial features, which improves face training datasets and recognition performances. Our system is tested on Head pose dataset [4] and achieved promising results in face recognition and verification.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents the proposed approach. Section 3 exposes the experimental results. Finally, section 4 concludes the paper with suggestions for future research.

2 Proposed Method

The proposed method, EVMPR (see Figure 1), consists of generating reduced facial representation in different poses from a single view based on multivariate polynomial regression between correlated facial features. First, facial features are extracted from images. Second, a classifier is trained for selecting relevant features. The correlation between features is then studied in order to optimize the estimation of views' features. Missing feature vectors are generated using multivariate polynomial regression.

Feature extraction consists of extracting a set of discriminating features from an image that well describe the face. In this paper, we applied the histogram of local binary patterns, LBPH [1], as a case of study, to extract texture feature representation from face images. Actually, as this study focuses on the estimation of features

Figure 1. Proposed method

related to pose, the use of a descriptor of spatial information is important. In addition, LBPH is commonly used to enhance face recognition due to its discriminating strength, calculation easiness and fast execution compared to other descriptors.

Feature selection corresponds to the reduction of features number by choosing the most relevant features for easier and fast training process. In this paper, we used Extremely Randomized Trees [3] for feature selection, which combines the results of multiple uncorrelated decision trees collected in a forest to output its classification result. Extremely Randomized Trees algorithm is faster compared to other tree ensemble classifiers like Random Forest in terms of computational cost, and therefore execution time. In fact, this algorithm saves time because the whole procedure is the same, but it randomly chooses the split point without calculating the optimal one. Each feature is indexed in descending order according to the Gini Importance. Then, the model selects the top features according to the number of the most important features chosen. The decision criteria for feature selection are "Gini" for the Gini impurity and "entropy" for the information gain.

$$Entropy(S) = \sum_{i=1}^c P_i \text{Log}_2(P_i) \quad (1)$$

where c is the number of unique class labels and P_i the proportion of rows with output label is i .

Feature correlation aims to study the relation between facial features and identify the features which are more correlated from the correlation matrix [5] in order to generate features of desired poses from the available poses. From the correlation matrix of facial features, we notice an important interdependence between some features. We defined two experiments in order to see the effect of correlation-based feature estimation in face recognition accuracy. In a first experience, each feature in the desired view was estimated from only the feature of the same index in the frontal view. Then, in a second experience, each feature was estimated as a function of the feature in the same index with a set of the most correlated features. Experiments showed that correlation-based feature estimation is more precise and gave better results than separately feature by feature estimation.

Multivariate Polynomial Regression [14] estimates the relationship between features in different facial views. In this research, every feature, in the predicted pose, is estimated from the feature of the same index in the available views. First, we trained the regressor to look for the relationship between features in all poses according to the equation (2). And for optimal parameters of the model, we collect a training dataset of persons with the whole poses. Then, in the test step, the feature vector in the desired pose is estimated from the available poses according to the relationship between them.

$$f_{i_{pose_2}} = \sum_{j=1}^N \left(a f_{i_{pose_1}}^j + b_1 f_{c1}^j + b_2 f_{c2}^j + b_3 f_{c3}^j + \dots + b_m f_{cm}^j \right) \quad (2)$$

Where $f_{i_{pose_2}}$ is the feature of index i in pose 2 and $f_{c1}^j \dots f_{cm}^j$ are respectively the features of highest correlation coefficient in the correlation matrix.

3 EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

Many experiments were made to optimise the estimation of feature vectors in different poses from Head Pose dataset. Actually, the feature vector estimated at a given pose is optimized when it satisfies two conditions; On the one hand, the minimum distance between the test vector and the vectors estimated at the same pose of different persons corresponds to the true identity. On the other hand, by integrating the estimated vectors into the training set, the performance improves and the minimum distance between the test vector and the vectors of different persons in different poses corresponds to the true identity and converges to the same pose.

In the feature study, 185 out of 256 LBPH most important features are chosen by the Extremely Randomized Tree classifier. Then, from the correlation matrix,

Figure 2. Improving face recognition with features generation in the case of many missing views

Table 1. Face recognition accuracy (%) using EVMPR for features generation in the case of many missing views from Head pose dataset [4]

Classifier	Accuracy(%)						
	Exp1	Exp2	Exp3	Exp4	Exp5	Exp6	Exp7
Decision Tree(DT)	26.66	48.88	57.77	78.88	87.77	95.55	100
K-nearest neighbors(KNN)	18.88	41.11	46.66	57.77	75.55	81.11	87.77
Random Forest(RF)	21.22	47.77	72.22	72.22	88.88	96.66	100
Support Vector Machine(SVM)	41.11	47.77	53.33	53.33	51.11	53.33	55.55
Logistic Regression(LR)	58.88	67.77	90.00	90.00	96.66	98.88	100
Multi-Layer Perceptron(MLP)	27.77	37.77	52.22	52.22	50.00	68.88	81.11
Extra Tree(ET)	22.22	66.66	85.55	85.55	88.88	94.44	100
Sum of Absolute Differences(SAD)	61.11	68.88	88.88	88.88	97.77	100	100

the indexes of the most correlated features are saved and used for better feature estimation. This study aims to reduce the number of feature representation for faster computations. In addition, the correlation between features gave more precision of features estimation. First, the estimation of facial features was optimised for one missing pose while testing with different numbers of correlated features and polynomial degree according to the recognition accuracy, as well as execution time. The obtained results show that multivariate polynomial regression using at least the 5 most correlated features in second-degree regression can be an optimized feature-

view estimator. Then, the results were generalized for multiple missing views as presented in Figure 2. In the first experience (Exp1), the face recognition was evaluated in the case of one facial view per person. From the second to the seventh experience (Exp2...Exp7), the estimation of pose (15...90) was added to the training dataset (Table. 1). The main objective of this study is to optimise the estimation of facial feature in various poses using the minimum of training poses. The more poses used for training, the best results obtained. We find that 7 poses are enough to get the optimal precision. Therefore, the add of poses does not improve precision but augments computation time.

4 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, a new approach was introduced to improve cross-pose face recognition in the case of insufficient poses in the training dataset. EVMPR consists of feature vector generation basing on multivariate polynomial regression between correlated features in different views. The main contribution of this work is to generate reduced representations of faces in different views with less computation complexity and optimized execution time. Significantly, this approach can fast improve face sets for providing models with much needed facial views representations. The experiment in Head pose dataset showed that this method gave significant accuracy improvement in face recognition. Thanks to the simplicity of our method, it can be easily embedded in different face recognition pipelines. In future works, we intend to extend the proposed study to be applied for face recognition in the wild.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research work was realized in collaboration between Sofia Technologies Company and CES-lab in the National Engineering School of Sfax. This project is carried out under the MOBIDOC scheme, funded by the EU through the EMORI program and managed by the ANPR.

References

1. Farah Deeba, Aftab Ahmed, Hira Memon, Fayaz Ali Dharejo, and Abddul Ghaffar. Lbph-based enhanced real-time face recognition. *Int. J. Adv. Comput. Sci. Appl*, 10(5):274–280, 2019.
2. Jiankang Deng, Jia Guo, Niannan Xue, and Stefanos Zafeiriou. Arcface: Additive angular margin loss for deep face recognition. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 4690–4699, 2019.
3. Pierre Geurts, Damien Ernst, and Louis Wehenkel. Extremely randomized trees. *Machine learning*, 63(1):3–42, 2006.

4. Nicolas Gourier, Daniela Hall, and James L Crowley. Estimating face orientation from robust detection of salient facial structures. In *FG Net workshop on visual observation of deictic gestures*, volume 6. Citeseer, 2004.
5. Mark Andrew Hall. Correlation-based feature selection for machine learning. 1999.
6. Jingtuo Liu, Yafeng Deng, Tao Bai, Zhengping Wei, and Chang Huang. Targeting ultimate accuracy: Face recognition via deep embedding. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1506.07310*, 2015.
7. Weiyang Liu, Yandong Wen, Zhiding Yu, Ming Li, Bhiksha Raj, and Le Song. Sphreface: Deep hypersphere embedding for face recognition. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 212–220, 2017.
8. Alessandra Lumini, Loris Nanni, and Sheryl Brahnam. Ensemble of texture descriptors and classifiers for face recognition. *Applied Computing and Informatics*, 13(1):79–91, 2017.
9. Iacopo Masi, Tal Hassner, Anh Tuan Tran, and Gérard Medioni. Rapid synthesis of massive face sets for improved face recognition. In *2017 12th IEEE International Conference on Automatic Face & Gesture Recognition (FG 2017)*, pages 604–611. IEEE, 2017.
10. Iacopo Masi, Yue Wu, Tal Hassner, and Prem Natarajan. Deep face recognition: A survey. In *2018 31st SIBGRAPI conference on graphics, patterns and images (SIBGRAPI)*, pages 471–478. IEEE, 2018.
11. Thu Nguyen-Phuoc, Chuan Li, Lucas Theis, Christian Richardt, and Yong-Liang Yang. Hologan: Unsupervised learning of 3d representations from natural images. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision*, pages 7588–7597, 2019.
12. Nicolas Pinto, James J DiCarlo, and David D Cox. How far can you get with a modern face recognition test set using only simple features? In *2009 IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 2591–2598. IEEE, 2009.
13. Soumyadip Sengupta, Jun-Cheng Chen, Carlos Castillo, Vishal M Patel, Rama Chellappa, and David W Jacobs. Frontal to profile face verification in the wild. In *2016 IEEE Winter Conference on Applications of Computer Vision (WACV)*, pages 1–9. IEEE, 2016.
14. Priyanka Sinha. Multivariate polynomial regression in data mining: methodology, problems and solutions. *International Journal of Scientific and Engineering Research*, 4(12):962–965, 2013.
15. Yi Sun. *Deep learning face representation by joint identification-verification*. The Chinese University of Hong Kong (Hong Kong), 2015.
16. Mei Wang and Weihong Deng. Deep face recognition: A survey. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1804.06655*, 2018.
17. Egor Zakharov, Aliaksandra Shysheya, Egor Burkov, and Victor Lempitsky. Few-shot adversarial learning of realistic neural talking head models. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision*, pages 9459–9468, 2019.
18. Jian Zhao, Lin Xiong, Jayashree Karlekar, Jianshu Li, Fang Zhao, Zhecan Wang, Sugiri Pranata, Shengmei Shen, Shuicheng Yan, and Jiashi Feng. Dual-agent gans for photorealistic and identity preserving profile face synthesis. In *NIPS*, volume 2, page 3, 2017.
19. Zhenyao Zhu, Ping Luo, Xiaogang Wang, and Xiaoou Tang. Multi-view perceptron: a deep model for learning face identity and view representations. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, pages 217–225, 2014.